

Article

Cybersecurity Requirements for Medical Devices in the EU and US - A Comparison and Gap Analysis

Max Ostermann¹, Stephen Gilbert^{1*}, and Oscar Freyer^{1*†}

¹ Else Kröner Fresenius Center for Digital Health, TUD Dresden University of Technology, Dresden, Germany

* Equal contribution as senior author

† Correspondence: oscar.freyer@tu-dresden.de

Abstract: The increasing use of connected medical devices (cMDs) has led to substantial cybersecurity challenges, putting patient safety and the integrity of healthcare infrastructures at risk. This study provides an analysis of regulatory guidance on medical device cybersecurity in the European Union (guidance document of Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG) 2019-16 revision 1) and the United States (US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) Guidance on Cybersecurity), identifying their strengths and gaps. The study compares these documents with a baseline requirements framework derived from international standards and best practices, revealing gaps in the thematic areas of “Cryptography,” “Consent,” and “Source Code/Software Development.” In the second step, the guidance documents were compared with real-world cybersecurity incidents, showing that the current guidance documents would successfully help to mitigate the weaknesses of important vulnerability examples while recommendations are missing in both guidance documents, but more so in MDCG 2019-16, for the most important weaknesses. This study highlights the need for future guidance documents to be clearer in scope and to close existing gaps to ultimately allow safer medical devices.

Keywords: medical devices; cybersecurity; regulatory science

1. Introduction

Over the last few years and through the widespread distribution of software in medical devices (MD) [1,2] and an increase in cyberattacks on critical healthcare infrastructure [3,4], cybersecurity has become a significant topic for manufacturers, users, and regulators of MDs. This is, on the one hand, reflected by an increasing number of regulations concerning MD cybersecurity [5] and, on the other hand, by an increase in manufacturers describing cybersecurity features in their documentation, including defensive mechanisms, response systems, or rigorous testing[6].

The aim of MDs is to fulfill their intended purpose effectively and, at the same time, be safe [7]. However, the use of MDs, in general, also carries risks, which can be caused by many possible aspects of the device. The use of software in medical devices connected to the internet adds potentially harmful aspects of cybersecurity to the device profile, which could exacerbate existing risks or even introduce new ones [5]. For example, a connected insulin pump could be targeted by malicious actors who could then change the insulin dosage and potentially harm the patient. Furthermore, the pump could be the entry point to a healthcare provider's system, allowing them to cause further damage to the provider, e.g., through a ransomware attack [8,9].

Research indicates that MDs connected via networks (cMDs), especially in remote patient monitoring (RPM) or hospital-at-home (HaH) settings, provide a large attack surface to arbitrary actors [10,11]. This could include attacks on the connected devices themselves, the provider's infrastructure, hospitals, and patients, and could be conducted via various attack vectors or mechanisms [10]. Such attacks could then, if adequate risk mitigation were not in place, lead to patient harm, as described in the example above, where the incorrect dosage of insulin could cause a hyper- or hypoglycemic coma [11]. Therefore, a device's digital capabilities, its ability to connect to networks, and the implementation of cybersecurity features significantly influence its benefit-risk profile[5].

To prevent, consider or mitigate these risks, a diverse set of standards and best practices has been proposed by international standardization bodies, national authorities, and researchers [12], e.g., IEC 81001-5-1 about the security of health software and health IT systems [13], the NIST Cybersecurity Framework [14], AAMI TIR57 for the risk management of MDs [15], IEEE 2621 for wireless diabetes device security [16], or IEC/TR 60601-4-5, a standard for safety-related technical security specifications [17]. These standards can be categorized as process standards (e.g., IEC 81001-5-1) that provide requirements on how a process should be conducted without providing extensive details on technical aspects. This is achieved primarily through product-orientated standards (e.g., IEC/TR 60601-4-5), which provide specific requirements, such as security specifications for certain products.

To ensure that manufacturers secure their devices against threats, and often based on the aforementioned best practices and standards, policies and guidelines by authorities such as the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and EU Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG) have been put in place, amending the already existing regulations for MD clearance or approval [5]. Those laws and policies define a set of requirements and recommendations and include technical principles, e.g., regarding network security, management aspects such as risk management, and process requirements, e.g., regarding secure development.

In the EU, requirements for the cybersecurity of MDs are defined on a high level in Regulation 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council on medical devices (MDR), further detailed in MDGC guidance. In the US, high-level requirements are defined in the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (FD&C Act), further detailed by FDA guidance

[5]. Two documents are particularly important for the cybersecurity of medical devices prior to their market release: revision 1 of the “Guidance on Cybersecurity for medical devices” by the MDCG (MDCG 2019-16) for the EU [18], and “Cybersecurity in Medical Devices: Quality System Considerations and Content of Premarket Submissions” (FDA_Cyber) by the FDA [19]. The goal of those documents is to provide manufacturers and regulators with a clearly defined rule set. However, the extent to which these new regulatory efforts are effective and lead to an improved security situation for MDs has yet to be evaluated. Some researchers and regulatory experts criticized guidance documents as being too superficial and having little practical relevance, thus leading to increased costs without improvement [5].

To evaluate the effectiveness of and potential gaps in current guidelines, this study aims to address three research questions. Firstly, do MDCG 2019-16 and FDA_Cyber comprehensively cover relevant cybersecurity aspects and identify potential gaps? Secondly, could adherence to these frameworks effectively prevent cybersecurity incidents? Thirdly, is the style and structure of guidance set out in MDCG 2019-16 and FDA_Cyber appropriate and helpful regarding the specificity and level of detail?

2. Methods

To answer the research questions, a multistep approach was taken. First, a set of cybersecurity requirements for MDs was developed based on existing standards and frameworks. Second, MDCG 2019-16 and FDA_Cyber were compared with each other and with our set of cybersecurity requirements. Third, a set of incidents described in the literature was analyzed to define the weakness that led to the incident. Then, the guidelines and the requirements set were mapped against the incidents to assess whether they would have been prevented by following one of the guidelines or our requirements list. Fourth, we describe an overview of existing gaps in current guidance.

2.1 Development of the set of cybersecurity requirements

To assess whether the requirements and recommendations provided in MDCG 2019-16 and FDA_Cyber cover relevant aspects of MD cybersecurity, we first developed a baseline set of cybersecurity requirements. This set was based on cybersecurity best practices relevant for MDs from recognized entities (Open Worldwide Application Security Project (OWASP) Foundation), international standardization bodies (International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and International Organization for Standardisation (ISO)), national standardization bodies (AAMI), and national authorities (National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnologie (BSI)). The requirements were grouped into broader topics. The initial draft was then evaluated by a second researcher. The requirements were updated based on this feedback.

2.2 Comparison of frameworks

To assess the overlap between MDCG 2019-16 and FDA_Cyber, we extracted each requirement of the documents, labeled them, and grouped them under a higher-level theme. We then mapped requirements and compared them with each other in a table to identify common areas, areas of application, and potential gaps.

2.3 Comparison against the proposed requirements list

The developed set of cybersecurity requirements was mapped against MDCG 2019-16 and FDA_Cyber in a tabular approach to assess the comprehensiveness and quality of these cybersecurity guidances. A requirement was considered to be represented if it was explicitly mentioned. In the statistical evaluation of the degree of coverage, a value of 1 was assigned in this case. If, on the other hand, the aspect was only mentioned implicitly or incompletely, a value of 0.5 was assigned. Common areas, requirements, and areas of application were identified, and gaps were described.

2.4 Incident mapping

To assess whether compliance with MDCG 2019-16 and FDA_Cyber would have a positive effect on the security of MDs, we retrospectively analyzed data of cyberattacks on MDs published by the US Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA). The CISA publishes reports on attacks on their website and assigns common vulnerabilities and exposures (CVE) codes, linking them to the CVE database. Medical device-related CISA advisories are labeled as 'ICSMA.' For our analysis, we used the CISA advisories for the top ten vulnerabilities identified by Mejía-Granda et al. (2024) [20]. We exported the data for each example and described each vulnerability. We then analyzed whether measures to mitigate the vulnerability were included as requirements in MDCG 2019-16, FDA_Cyber, and the proposed requirements list, and thus could have been avoided if the guidance had been followed. The coverage of a vulnerability was rated on a three-step scale, from 'Covered' if the guidance explicitly mentioned the corresponding practices or specifications, to 'Implicitly Covered' if they are not directly named, but the descriptions indicate that they are covered, to 'Not Covered'. Any gaps in the guidance documents were identified and described.

3. Results

3.1 Mapping of guidance documents and the requirements list

The initial creation of the cybersecurity requirements list defines 13 thematic areas that are relevant for the secure development and deployment of cMDs: General Principles, Authorisation & Access Control, Data Protection & Privacy, Cryptography, Architecture, Network, Passwords, Resilience, Source Code & Software Development, Risk Management, Testing, Consent, and Third Party Components. In addition to the 13 areas defined in our requirements list, FDA_cyber and MDCG 2019-16 contained several recommendations for

the submission documentation and user communication. While these are relevant for the approval of MDs, they do not provide process or specification requirements and, thus, are not part of the defined requirements list. A total of 112 requirements were categorized under these areas. The complete set of requirements, including descriptions and references, is provided in **Appendix I, Table S1**.

The requirements and recommendations provided in the two guidance documents were distributed into the same categories defined for the requirements list. For the FDA guidance, that led to a total of 141 requirements, including those for documentation and user instructions. Similarly, the MDCG guidance contains 156 requirements. The complete mapping of the documents is provided in **Appendix I, Tables S2-S3**.

3.2 Gap analysis of guidance documents

The mapping of MDCG 2019-16 and FDA_Cyber shows a varying degree of coverage of the individual thematic areas, while the overall coverage was medium for both but lower for MDCG 2019-16 (41%, 46/112) than for FDA_Cyber (47%, 52.5/112). While “Testing” and “Risk Management” were well represented with a coverage of 100 % (5/5) for testing, respectively 91% (10/11) for “Risk Management,” the largest gaps exist for both documents in the areas “Consent” (0%, 0/0). The coverage of the general principles was slightly higher in MDCG 2019-16 (72%, 6.5/9), while FDA_Cyber covered requirements regarding “Architecture” (70%, 7/10) better. Besides “Consent,” the largest gaps remain in the area of “Network” for the FDA guidance and in the areas of “Cryptography” and “Source Code & Software Development” for MDCG 2019-16. **Figure 1** shows the coverage of the requirements by category. A table view of the complete gap analysis can be found in **Appendix I, Tables S4**.

Area	FDA_Cyber		MDCG 2019-16	
01_General Principles	6/9	67%	6.5/9	72%
02_Authentication & Access Control	5.5/16	34%	4.5/16	28%
03_Data Protection & Privacy	3/13	23%	3/13	23%
04_Cryptography	4.5/8	56%	0.5/8	6%
05_Architecture	7/10	70%	4/10	40%
06_Network	1.5/8	19%	4/8	50%
07_Passwords	3/6	50%	3/6	50%
08_Resilience	1/5	20%	1/5	20%
09_Source Code/Software Development	3/7	43%	0/7	0%
10_Risk Management	10/11	91%	10/11	91%
11_Testing	5/5	100%	5/5	100%
12_Consent	0/4	0%	0/4	0%
13_Third Party Components	4/10	40%	4.5/10	45%
Total	53.5/112	48%	46/112	41%

Figure 1. Mapping of MDCG 2019-16, FDA_Cyber, and the developed requirements list and the degree of coverage.

3.3 Vulnerability Analysis

Except for three CVEs, the weaknesses and exploits that led to a vulnerability are well covered by measures in the guidance documents. The three CVEs not explicitly covered by MDCG 2019-16 can be traced back to one weakness: CWE-798, Use of Hard-coded Credentials. While this weakness is considered in the FDA guidance, the MDCG 2019-16 does not name credentials in their no hard-coded passwords requirement.

Regarding the vulnerabilities, the results are more diverse. MDCG 2019-16 covers five CWEs, CWE 798 (Use of Hard-Coded Credentials), CWE 200 (Information Exposure), CWE 20 (Improper Input Validation), CWE 522 (Insufficiently Protected Credentials), and CWE 434 (Unrestricted Upload of Files with Dangerous Type) only implicitly. FDA_Cyber performs slightly better, with three CWEs being only implicitly covered: CWE 200 (Information Exposure), CWE 20 (Improper Input Validation), and CWE 434 (Unrestricted Upload of Files with Dangerous Type). **Figure 2** provides an overview of the vulnerabilities and whether these are covered by the guidance document.

CVE	Key Exploit	Mitigation/Detection	FDA_Cyber	MDCG 2019-16	Requirements List
2022-22766	Hard-coded credentials	Code Analysis/ Testing/ Documentation	Covered	Implicitly covered	Covered
2021-27410	Out-of-bounds write	Fuzzing/ vulnerability scanning	Covered	Covered	Covered
2018-14786#	Lacking Authentication	Code Analysis/ Testing/ Documentation	Covered	Covered	Covered
2018-4846#	Hard-coded credentials	Code Analysis/ Testing/ Documentation	Covered	Implicitly covered	Covered
2021-27408	Out-of-bounds read	Fuzzing/ vulnerability scanning	Covered	Covered	Covered
2021-32025	Privilege Escalation	Principle of least privileges, intrusion detection, MFA	Covered	Covered	Covered
2018-4845#	Privilege Escalation	Principle of least privileges, intrusion detection, MFA	Covered	Covered	Covered
2017-14006#	Hard-coded credentials	Code Analysis/ Testing/ Documentation	Covered	Implicitly covered	Covered
2016-8355#	Privilege Management/ insufficient authentication	Principle of least privileges, intrusion detection, MFA	Covered	Covered	Covered
2021-22156	Integer Overflow	Fuzzing/vulnerability scanning	Covered	Covered	Covered
CWE	Key Exploit	Mitigation/Detection	FDA_Cyber	MDCG 2019-16	Requirements List
798	Use of Hard-Coded Credentials	Code Analysis/ Testing/ Documentation	Covered	Implicitly covered	Covered
200	Information Exposure	Encrypt Data at all stages. No revealing data in error messages	Implicitly covered†*	Implicitly covered†*	Covered
20	Improper Input Validation	Input Sanitation	Implicitly covered†	Implicitly covered†	Covered
287	Improper Authentication	Code Analysis/ Testing/ Documentation	Covered	Covered	Covered
319	Cleartext Transmission of Sensitive Information	Encrypt Data in Transit	Covered	Covered	Covered
522	Insufficiently Protected Credentials	Encrypt Credentials/ Do not require transmission of unprotected credentials	Covered	Implicitly covered†*	Covered
523	Unprotected Transport of Credentials	Encrypt Credentials/ Do not require transmission of unprotected credentials	Covered	Covered	Covered
269	Improper Privilege Management	Principle of least privileges, intrusion detection, MFA	Covered	Covered	Covered
259	Use of Hard-Coded Password	Code Analysis/ Testing/ Documentation	Covered	Covered	Covered
434	Unrestricted Upload of Files with Dangerous Type	Enact controls for file uploads	Implicitly covered†	Implicitly covered†	Implicitly covered†

Figure 2. Overview of vulnerabilities and their coverage in guidance documents. The selected CVE examples represent the most impactful medical device weaknesses identified by Mejía-Granda et al. (2024) [20]. The selected CWEs represent the 10 most common weaknesses, according to Bracciale et al. (2023) [21]. The table shows the coverage in the guidance documents and in the requirements list described earlier. *does not offer controls for the examples in CWE-200; † mentioned as part of testing; ‡ predates both guidance documents.

4. Discussion

4.1 Principal Results

In our analysis, we identified several gaps in current guidance documents, especially in the areas of “Cryptography,” “Consent,” and “Source Code & Software Development” for MDCG 2019-16, and in the areas “Consent” for FDA_Cyber. While the adherence to the principles, requirements, and recommendations of the guidance documents would successfully help to mitigate the weaknesses of the selected CVE examples, recommendations are missing in both guidance documents, but more so in MDCG 2019-16, with regard to the Top 10 Weaknesses (CWEs).

4.2 Evaluation of MDCG 2019-16

MDCG 2019-16 provides information on three cybersecurity domains: general principles such as ‘Security by design’ or ‘Defense in depth,’ which are defined and explained, and cybersecurity-related processes such as security risk management and technical specifications.

In order to be compliant with the general requirements of the MDR, this guidance prescribes the application of ‘Secure Design’ and defines it in eight principles. However, the description of these principles is rather superficial, and some principles are only introduced and defined but not properly addressed. This limits the effectiveness of the guidance, as no reference is made to further resources, e.g., OWASP. In addition, the guidance describes a list of security capabilities labeled as ‘indicative,’ which lack sufficient explanation, framing, or justification.

Risk management aspects take up a large part of the guidance and are explained in detail. Except for the link between risk management activities and the quality management system, a requirement according to, for example, IEC 81001-5-1, all important areas are covered. Only the final assessment of remaining cybersecurity risks as part of the benefit-risk analysis remains unclear, so it is uncertain how cybersecurity risks affect the overall benefit-risk profile [5].

In Chapter 3.6, MDCG 2019-16 provides an overview of the minimum IT requirements. It should be emphasized that these requirements should always be seen in the context of the

operating environment, a requirement that is also included in the list of requirements we have proposed. In addition, it is noted that MDs should also be independently cybersecure, since requirements for the operating environment are not within the scope of the MDR. Despite this focus, requirements for the MDs themselves remain vague. For example, penetration tests are only mentioned as a recommendation, although they are often treated as a de facto requirement by the notified bodies [22]. Also, important requirements that could prevent known vulnerabilities in MDs are not mentioned, e.g., input sanitization.

An anomaly in MDCG 2019-16 is the high level of detail in the requirements for user instructions and documentation, which contrasts with the general vagueness of the technical requirements. It seems somewhat unclear what the intended role of this guidance in general is. Although the chapters explaining basic principles could be the starting point for further activities by manufacturers, the lack of tangible methods and requirements and the lack of explanation of meaningful references could mean that this guidance is of little use to developers. Furthermore, simply following the guidance does not ensure that those weaknesses that are reported to frequently occur in medical devices are adequately addressed.

4.3 Gap analysis of guidance documents

Overall, it can be said that both guidance documents mention various important aspects and explain fundamental principles, but at the same time, neglect various technical principles that would be fundamental to the effective mitigation of vulnerabilities. FDA_Cyber performs slightly better than MDCG 2019-16.

A fundamental problem for both guidance documents is that their intended role and the level of their operation is unclear. On the one hand, certain aspects are only superficially explained or mentioned, while on the other hand, there are very specific requirements for other areas.

Major gaps in MDCG 2019-16 are in the area of “Authentication & Access Control”, as the document does not consider multi-factor authentication, the separation of authentication and authorization, detection of the change of authentication data, or the establishment of a root of trust through certificates. The consideration of “Data Protection & Privacy” is relatively low, with gaps in the areas of backup encryption and data minimization. It is concerning that there is only superficial guidance on cryptographic principles such as avoidance of hard-coded credentials. MDCG 2019-16 only requires the avoidance of hard-coded passwords without considering other credentials, which are part of one of the most common weaknesses in MDs [20,21]. However, it could be assumed that developers who fulfill the requirements regarding passwords will also follow the implicit requirement for the avoidance of hard-coded credentials in general.

Additionally, considerations of attack surface reduction, application of coding best practices, detection of unusual behavior, consent and purpose, and “No Security through Obscurity” are not appropriately covered.

There are similar gaps in the FDA guidance, where the separation of authentication and authorization, detection of the change of authentication data, unusual login attempts, or the establishment of a root of trust through certificates are not covered. The document specifies the requirement of secure data in rest, transit, and use only for sensitive data, which is too limiting, as other data could also be of interest to malicious actors. Most important is the lack of attention to network security principles, third-party auditing, detection of unusual behavior, consent and purpose, and the principle “No Security through Obscurity.”

4.4 Implications of real-world incident data

Current research shows that many vulnerabilities and weaknesses exist in medical devices on the market and that new ones are regularly found [20,21]. A review of the CVEs of the 10 most impactful medical device weaknesses, some of which predate the two guidance documents, shows that mitigation measures for these are already well represented in the current guidance. From this, it could be concluded that the mere existence of guidance is insufficient, but that manufacturers must also implement the principles mentioned in the guidance well. A possible approach to encourage stricter adherence could be the exploration of fines in cases of gross misconduct.

The picture for the 10 most common weaknesses is somewhat more mixed. Here, too, most are already covered by the existing guidance documents. However, there are some CWEs that are not explicitly covered by the guidance documents. For MDCG 2019-16, there are five such CWEs, while FDA_Cyber does slightly better with two not explicitly covered CWEs. The uncovered CWEs overlap with the gaps in the guidance documents that we have identified.

Some of the CWEs that are covered in the guidance could easily be avoided by careful developers, e.g., hard-coded credentials or privilege issues. It is concerning that these CWEs remain in on-market devices. Other vulnerabilities are harder to detect and to prevent, e.g., out-of-bounds errors. However, careful developers should expect this type of mistake and extensively test the device to detect it.

Although the direct influence of the guidance documents on preventing these CWEs is probably small, guidance documents should close this gap and define requirements for CWEs that have not yet been adequately addressed.

4.5 Considerations for future guidance

For further development of guidance material, it should first be defined what the exact purpose of the guidance is to be and at which level of detail principles should be explained or requirements formulated. To minimize inconsistencies, aspects that do not serve this purpose, or that are not at the agreed level of detail, should not be mentioned.

One problem with defining technical specifications very precisely is that they may quickly become irrelevant because they no longer correspond to the state of the art. This can be

avoided by linking to regularly updated sources, or by applying standardization principles such as those in IEEE 2601, where certain requirements are deliberately not formulated.

To solve the current problems regarding the document structure, in which requirements are unclear, categorized, listed multiple times, or integrated into running text, the application of the principles of SMART standards could be carried out [23], i.e., to develop a SMART guidance. In contrast to current standards and guidance documents, SMART standards are machine-readable, thus simplifying the identification and implementation of requirements and automating them in the future.

For future guidance documents, it is also important to clearly define which requirements apply to which type of MDs. For example, cybersecurity requirements for web-based applications, mobile devices, stationary devices, and IoT devices differ significantly. One way to address this would be to provide guides for different use cases subordinate to the general guidelines that formulate the general principles and requirements.

4.6 Future research

Future research should address two aspects: what constitutes appropriate and helpful guidance and to what extent guidance materials and standards make MDs safer. In the first area, the perspectives of relevant stakeholders, such as manufacturers, regulators, or standardization bodies, should be systematically captured and analyzed. The examination of whether guidance is effective should also be empirically analyzed. To do this, the collection of stakeholder perspectives on the deployment could also be used, but data from devices in the market could also be collected. The method we propose in this paper of evaluating publicly available CVEs and CWEs could be one component of this. On the basis of these findings, better and more effective guidance documents could then be written.

4.7 Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the developed requirements list contains ambiguity regarding the level of detail. While some recommendations are high-level, others are very detailed and potentially not appropriate for all kinds of devices. Additionally, there could be inconsistencies regarding the categorization of some aspects, as they could fall under multiple thematic areas. Second, only MD-specific guidelines were considered in this analysis. In the EU, there are additional regulations related to cybersecurity, including the Cyber Resilience Act, the Cybersecurity Act, and the NIS Directive. Third, the categorization of the requirements from the guidance documents to the 13 thematic areas is susceptible to bias as it was based on the judgment of the reviewers. Additionally, requirements could be relevant for more than one area. Fourth, the rigidity of the statistical evaluation of the gap analysis of the two guidance documents could be limited by different levels of granularity between the two documents and the checklist. The results should only be interpreted with reference to the complete requirements, which are listed in Appendix I, Tables S4. Fifth, the analysis only

retrospectively looked at known vulnerabilities and weaknesses. Thus, the validity regarding new future (and previously unknown) vulnerabilities is limited.

4.8 Conclusions

Cybersecurity vulnerabilities in MDs can compromise the safety and effectiveness of these products and expose patients and the healthcare infrastructure to risks. The secure development and deployment of MDs is required by regulations and explained in more detail in guidance materials. However, these guidance materials are sometimes inadequately formulated, have an unclear scope, and contain gaps. These gaps could lead to manufacturers not adequately addressing cyber security in their products, creating vulnerabilities. Future guidance documents should be clearer in scope and close existing gaps. Overall, product safety depends primarily on how well manufacturers implement well-known principles, although effective guidelines can support manufacturers, and regulatory enforcement can find and remove non-compliance.

5. References

1. Ceross A, Bergmann J. Evaluating the Presence of Software-as-a-Medical-Device in the Australian Therapeutic Goods Register. *Prosthesis Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute*; 2021 Sep;3(3):221–228. doi: 10.3390/prosthesis3030022
2. Ceross A, Bergmann J. Tracking the Presence of Software as a Medical Device in US Food and Drug Administration Databases: Retrospective Data Analysis. *JMIR Biomed Eng* 2021 Nov 3;6(4):e20652. doi: 10.2196/20652
3. Munoz Cornejo G, Lee J, Russell BA. A thematic analysis of ransomware incidents among United States hospitals, 2016–2022. *Health Technol* 2024 Jul 9; doi: 10.1007/s12553-024-00890-3
4. Neprash HT, McGlave CC, Cross DA, Virnig BA, Puskarich MA, Huling JD, Rozenshtein AZ, Nikpay SS. Trends in Ransomware Attacks on US Hospitals, Clinics, and Other Health Care Delivery Organizations, 2016-2021. *JAMA Health Forum* 2022 Dec 29;3(12):e224873. PMID:36580326
5. Freyer O, Jahed F, Ostermann M, Rosenzweig C, Werner P, Gilbert S. Consideration of Cybersecurity in the Benefit-Risk Analysis of Medical Devices: A Scoping Review and Recommendations. 2024. doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-4816554/v1
6. Stern AD, Gordon WJ, Landman AB, Kramer DB. Cybersecurity features of digital medical devices: an analysis of FDA product summaries. *BMJ Open British Medical Journal Publishing Group*; 2019 Jun 1;9(6):e025374. PMID:31256020
7. European Parliament, European Council. Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (Text with EEA relevance)Text with EEA relevance. Apr 5, 2017.

8. Williams PA, Woodward AJ. Cybersecurity vulnerabilities in medical devices: a complex environment and multifaceted problem. *Med Devices Auckl NZ* 2015 Jul 20;8:305–316. PMID:26229513
9. Willing M, Dresen C, Haverkamp U, Schinzel S. Analyzing medical device connectivity and its effect on cyber security in german hospitals. *BMC Med Inform Decis Mak* 2020 Sep 29;20(1):246. doi: 10.1186/s12911-020-01259-y
10. Yaqoob T, Abbas H, Atiquzzaman M. Security Vulnerabilities, Attacks, Countermeasures, and Regulations of Networked Medical Devices—A Review. *IEEE Commun Surv Tutor* 2019;21(4):3723–3768. doi: 10.1109/COMST.2019.2914094
11. Ostermann M, Freyer O, Jahed F, Rosenzweig C, Gilbert S. Cybersecurity in the HaH: Assessment of Patient Risks when using IoMT devices. 2024.
12. Ostermann M, Freyer O, Jahed F, Gilbert S. Device Management in the Internet of Medical Things: A Systematic Review. *Research Square*; 2024. doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-5534497/v1
13. International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). IEC 81001-5-1:2021. 2021. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/standard/76097.html> [accessed Jul 10, 2024]
14. National Institute of Standards and Technology. NIST Cybersecurity Framework 2.0. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 2023 p. NIST CSWP 29. Report No.: NIST CSWP 29. doi: 10.6028/NIST.CSWP.29
15. Association for the Advancement of Medical Instrumentation (AAMI). AAMI TIR57:2016 (R2023). 2023. Available from: <https://webstore.ansi.org/standards/aami/aamitir572016r2023> [accessed Jul 10, 2024]
16. IEEE. IEEE/UL Standard for Wireless Diabetes Device Security: Information Security Requirements for Connected Diabetes Solutions. 2022. doi: 10.1109/IEEESTD.2022.9773069
17. International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). IEC/TR 60601-4-5:2021. 2021. Available from: <https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/64703> [accessed Dec 18, 2024]
18. Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG). MDCG 2019-16 Rev. 1 Guidance on Cybersecurity for medical devices. 2020 Jul. Available from: https://health.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-01/md_cybersecurity_en.pdf [accessed Mar 5, 2024]
19. U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA). Cybersecurity in Medical Devices: Quality System Considerations and Content of Premarket Submissions. 2023 Sep. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/media/119933/download>
20. Mejía-Granda CM, Fernández-Alemán JL, Carrillo-de-Gea JM, García-Berná JA. Security vulnerabilities in healthcare: an analysis of medical devices and software. *Med Biol Eng Comput* 2024 Jan 1;62(1):257–273. doi: 10.1007/s11517-023-02912-0

21. Bracciale L, Loreti P, Bianchi G. Cybersecurity vulnerability analysis of medical devices purchased by national health services. *Sci Rep Nature Publishing Group*; 2023 Nov 9;13(1):19509. doi: 10.1038/s41598-023-45927-1
22. IGNB. Questionnaire "Cybersecurity for Medical Devices - Audit". 2023. Available from: https://www.ig-nb.de/fileadmin/user_upload/ig-nb/Questionnaire_Cybersecurity_for_Medical_Devices_-_Audit_-_Version_1.pdf
23. International Organization for Standardization. ISO - IEC/ISO SMART. ISO. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/smart> [accessed Dec 21, 2024]

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe Program, as part of the project CYMEDSEC (101094218). The views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union, nor the granting authorities, can be held responsible for them. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the authors. This work was supported by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) as part of the Zukunftscluster SEMECO (03ZU1210BA).

During the preparation of this work, the authors used DeepL (DeepL SE), Grammarly (Grammarly, Inc), and ChatGPT (in versions GPT-3.5, GPT-4, and GPT-4o; OpenAI, Inc) to improve the grammar, spelling, and readability of the manuscript. After using these tools and services, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Author contributions: O.F., M.O., and S.G. developed the concept of the manuscript. M.O. created the first draft of the requirements list. O.F. and M.O. revised the requirements list. M.O. and O.F. extracted the data and conducted the comparative analysis. M.O. extracted the data from the CVE's and conducted the analysis. M.O. and O.F. wrote the first draft of the manuscript. O.F., M.O., and S.G. contributed to the writing, interpretation of the content, and editing of the manuscript, revising it critically for important intellectual content. M.O., O.F., and S.G. had final approval of the completed version. M.O., O.F., and S.G. take accountability for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

Conflicts of Interest: SG is an advisory group member of the Ernest & Young-coordinated "Study on Regulatory Governance and Innovation in the field of Medical Devices" conducted on behalf of the Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety of the European Commission. The authors declare the following competing interests. SG has or has had consulting relationships with Una Health GmbH, Lindus Health Ltd, Flo Ltd, Thymia Ltd, FORUM Institut für Management GmbH, High-Tech Gründerfonds Management GmbH, and Ada Health GmbH, and he holds share options in Ada Health GmbH. OF has a leadership role and holds stock in WhalesDontFly GmbH. MO declares no competing interests.

Appendix I

Table S1. Cybersecurity requirements for medical devices.

Code	Aspect	Description	Source
01_General Principles			
GNRL_1	Life-Cycle Approach	Security is part of the software development and life cycle.	TR_03161, IEC 81001-5-1, AAMI_TIR57
GNRL_2	Security by Design (SbD)	The SbD principle shall be considered during the entire development process	ISO 11073-40102:2022; BSI TR-03161-2 "O.Arch_1"
GNRL_3	Security by Default	An application shall automatically be configured in the most secure way	ISO 11073-40102:2022
GNRL_4	Usable Security	Accept the human-factor to cybersecurity. Ensure security features are user-friendly, adaptable so users don't attempt to circumvent them	NIST SP 800-63B, ISO 9241-210
GNRL_5	No Security through Obscurity	Rely on well-documented, tested and implemented security measures instead of relying on hidden self-made mechanisms	ANSM R3; BSI TR-03161-2 O.Cryp_2, IEC 81001-5-1
GNRL_6	Security in Context	Consider the device in its environment, minimisation of physical access ports, physical security	IEEE_2621.2, IEC 81001-5-1
GNRL_7	Third Party Auditing	Conduct regular audits of third-party components and apply necessary updates promptly	NIST Cybersecurity Framework; IEC 62304 5.1.5 ; BSI TR-03161-2 "O.Arch_1", ANSM R6,R37
GNRL_8	End-Of-Life	Create a process for securely decommissioning systems and sanitizing data	ANSM, SK, BSI, NIST CSF 2.0 ID.AM-08, IEC 81001-5-1
GNRL_9	Documentation	The manufacturer should maintain a documentation following industry best practices	
02_Auth & Access Control			
AUTH_1	Principle of Least Privileges	Every user should only have the least amount of privileges they need to use the application	ISO 11073-40102:2022, IEC 81001-5-1
AUTH_2	Role Based Access Control	Access control should follow the role based model	ISO 11073-40102:2022
AUTH_3	Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA)	Implement MFA for all sensitive data access points	TR_03161
AUTH_4	Separation of authentication and authorization	Separate implementation of authentication and authorization	TR_03161
AUTH_5	Session Management	The manufacturer should have a concept for authentication, authorization (role concept) and termination of application sessions.	TR_03161
AUTH_6	Re-authentication in active use	Re-authentication after an appropriate period of time during which the application has been in permanent active use.	TR_03161, IEEE_2621.2
AUTH_7	Re-authentication after interruption	Re-authentication in case of interrupted application.	TR_03161, IEEE_2621.2
AUTH_8	Re-authentication after inactivity	Re-authentication after an appropriate period of time during which the application was not actively used.	TR_03161, IEEE_2621.2
AUTH_9	Invalidation of identification tokens	Invalidation of previously issued authentication tokens or session identifiers by the user.	TR_03161
AUTH_10	Change of authentication data	Sufficient authentication of the user to change the authentication data.	TR_03161

AUTH_11	Change of access parameters	Notification of the user when access parameters are changed.	TR_03161
AUTH_12	Deletion of identification tokens	Deletion of the authentication token or session identifier after the end of the application session.	TR_03161
AUTH_13	Access Logging	Enable logging for all access events and regularly review logs	ANSM R29,30
AUTH_14	Unusual login attempts	Inform the user about unusual login attempts	TR_03161, IEEE_2621.2
AUTH_15	Brute Force Login attempts	Prevent an unusually high number of login parameters from being tried.	TR_03161
AUTH_16	Root of trust	Signatures and message authentication codes should be verified by using a hardware-protected root of trust	IEEE_2621.2
03_Data Protection & Privacy			
DATA_1	Privacy-preserving design	Consideration of the processing of sensitive data in the design phase.	TR_03161
DATA_2	Minimal access to sensitive data	Dedicated access to encrypted storage or user data through interpreted code only if absolutely necessary.	TR_03161
DATA_3	Secure Data at Rest	Data is only stored in encrypted form, only decrypted for use, Encryption of locally stored data with a secure Device binding.	NIST CSF2.0 PR.DS, TR_03161
DATA_4	Secure Data at Transit	Data is only transmitted in encrypted form over secure channels	NIST CSF2.0 PR.DS, TR_03161
DATA_5	Secure Data at Use	Use of TEE, SMPC or other approaches	NIST CSF2.0 PR.DS, TR_03161
DATA_6	Encrypted Backups	No unencrypted sensitive data persisted in backups or in the browser cache.	TR_03161
DATA_7	No Key-logging	No recordings when entering sensitive data via the keyboard.	TR_03161
DATA_8	No clipboard exports	No export of sensitive data to the clipboard.	TR_03161
DATA_9	No export of biometric data or keys	No export of sensitive data (biometric data, keys) from its origin.	TR_03161
DATA_10	Blocking of screen access	No storage of screen content or access by third parties when displaying sensitive data.	TR_03161
DATA_11	Third-party data access	No access to sensitive data by third parties.	TR_03161
DATA_12	Data Minimisation	The manufacturer should follow principles of data minimisation and purpose limitation	TR_03161
DATA_13	Verifying data validity	Use signatures or message authentication codes to verify validity of data	IEEE_2621.2
04_Cryptography			
CRYP_1	Strong Cryptographic Algorithms	Use only strong, up-to-date algorithms like AES-256 and RSA-2048	BSI TR-03161-2 O.Cryp_3,4,5, IEEE_2621.2
CRYP_2	Key Management	Developers should key management best practices. Key management processes describe the secure generation, storage, distribution, and destruction of keys.	NIST SP 800-57 Part 1
CRYP_3	Strong Cryptographic Keys	Implement secure key management practices, including rotation and access control	BSI TR-03161-2 O.Arch_3
CRYP_4	Protection of cryptographic keys	Cryptographic keys should be protected against manipulation.	TR_03161, IEC 81001-5-1
CRYP_5	No hard-coded keys or other secrets	Keys should not be hard coded into the source code.	TR_03161

CRYP_6	Purpose limitation of cryptographic keys	One key should only be used for one purpose.	TR_03161
CRYP_7	Proven Implementations	Only use proven implementations and libraries of cryptographic protocols	
CRYP_8	Strong, secure random number generation	Generation of random values using a secure random number generator, with strong source of entropy	TR_03161, IEEE_2621.2
05_Architecture			
ARCH_1	Secure Update Mechanism	Secure software updates with cryptographic signatures and version controls	ISO 11073-40102:2022, IEC 81001-5-1
ARCH_2	Trusted update channels	Updated should be provided via a trusted channel.	TR_03161
ARCH_3	Ensure application of updates	Inform the application about safety- related updates.	TR_03161
ARCH_4	Central logging system	The application should have a central logging system.	TR_03161
ARCH_5	Endpoint security	Implementation of security features on all endpoints.	TR_03161, IEC 81001-5-1
ARCH_6	Localised processing logic	Localised processing logic of the web application on the server side.	TR_03161
ARCH_7	Management interfaces	Prevent unwanted access via management interfaces.	TR_03161
ARCH_8	Defense in Depth	The architecture should be designed to provide Defense in Depth	IEC 81001-5-1
ARCH_9	Attack Surface reduction	The architecture should be designed to minimise the attach surface.	IEC 81001-5-1
ARCH_10	Design/Architecture reviews	Architecture should be reviewed on a regular basis	IEC 81001-5-1
06_Network			
NETW_1	Network Security	Secure all network communications with VPNs or encrypted protocols like TLS	ANSM R23-27, NIST SP 800-52 Rev. 2
NETW_2	Encryption of Network Communication	Network communication is encrypted throughout with mutual authentication and following the current state of the art.	TR_03161
NETW_3	Certificate Chain	Verification of the entire certificate chain.	TR_03161
NETW_4	Support for certificate-pinning	Support for certificate-pinning if appropriate.	TR_03161
NETW_5	Validation of Backend Systems	Validate the integrity and authenticity of application/backend system responses.	TR_03161
NETW_6	Log Files	Providing complete log files for all established connections.	TR_03161
NETW_7	Firewalls	Protection of the network by firewalls.	TR_03161
NETW_8	Separation of communication channels	Separation of trusted communication channels and untrusted channles. Trusted channels must ensure the integrity and confidentiality of channel data	IEEE_2621.2
07_Passwords			
PWRD_1	Strong Password Rules	Implement password complexity and rotation policies aligned with best practices, Apply password policies for complexity and rotation; Maintain cybersecurity usability considerations to prevent unreasonable password requirements (too lenient or too strict)	ANSM R10, TR_03161
PWRD_2	Display password strength when creating it	When creating the password, its strength should be displayed.	TR_03161
PWRD_3	Option for password changes	An application should have the option to change the password.	TR_03161

PWRD_4	Logging of password changes	Logging and information about changing and resetting of passwords.	TR_03161
PWRD_5	Storage of passwords	Use of cryptographically secure hashing algorithms and salts to store passwords.	TR_03161
PWRD_6	No hardcoded passwords	Passwords should not be hardcoded.	TR_03161
08_Resilience			
RESI_1	Detection of debug environment	The application should detect and prevent a startup in a development/debug environment.	TR_03161
RESI_2	Unusual user rights detection	Abort the start of the application in the event of unusual user rights.	TR_03161
RESI_3	Integrity check of end device	Integrity check of the mobile device before processing sensitive data.	TR_03161
RESI_4	Integrity check of backend system	Verification of the authenticity of the backend system before access.	TR_03161
RESI_5	Reverse engineering	Implement measures against reverse engineering.	TR_03161
09_Source Code/Software Development			
SOUR_1	Coding Best Practises	Follow secure coding guidelines, such as OWASP or CERT, and conduct regular code reviews	OWASP Secure Coding Practices; CERT Secure Coding, ASNM R37, IEC 81001-5-1
SOUR_2	Input sanitation	Inputs should be checked before processing.	TR_03161
SOUR_3	Prevention against injection functionalities	Preventive measures to protect the application from the injection of functionalities that are outside the developer's own sovereignty.	TR_03161
SOUR_4	No sensitive data in messages.	Messages and notifications should not contain sensitive data.	TR_03161
SOUR_5	Secure productive version	Complete removal of supportive development options and debug mechanisms in the productive version.	TR_03161, IEC 81001-5-1
SOUR_6	Secure development environment	Activating modern security mechanisms of the development environment.	TR_03161
SOUR_7	Automation Tools	Automatic detection of program errors and best practice violations	TR_03161
10_Risk Management			
RISK_1	Continuous Monitoring	Use appropriate level of real-time monitoring tools to detect and alert on potential security events; the monitoring should include publicly available incident and vulnerability databases	NIST CSF2.0 DE, ID.IM-02, IEC 81001-5-1, AAMI_TIR57, TR_03161
RISK_2	Incident Response Plan	Develop and test a formal incident response plan	ISO/IEC 27035, NIST CSF2.0 RS, ID.IM-04, IEC 81001-5-1, TR_03161
RISK_3	Threat Modeling	Create a comprehensive threat model identifying potential threats, vulnerabilities, assets, and adverse impacts	https://owasp.org/www-community/Threat_Modeling , NIST SP 800-30; IEC 80001-1, IEC 81001-5-1, AAMI_TIR57
RISK_4	Check vulnerability databases	Regularly assess the application against OWASP Top 10 vulnerabilities and CWE weaknesses	ANSM R37
RISK_5	User instructions	The manufacturer should inform the user about the safe handling of the product	TR_03161, IEC 81001-5-1
RISK_6	Quality Management System	Security activities should be performed on the basis of a documented quality management system	IEC 81001-5-1
RISK_7	Security Training	Security training should be provided to the users if needed and to the manufacturers staff	IEC 81001-5-1

RISK_8	Security Management	Risk	Security Risk Management should be implemented, e.g. by following ISO 14971, and should include threat modeling and risk estimation for each vulnerability and threat combination as well as a review of implemented security measures.	IEC 81001-5-1, AAMI_TIR57
RISK_9	User reporting		Users should be able to report security issues easily.	TR_03161, IEC 81001-5-1
RISK_10	Reporting of security-related issues		The manufacturer should report security related issues to authorities	IEC 81001-5-1
RISK_11	Benefit Risk analysis		The benefit-risk analysis should consider cybersecurity-related risks.	AAMI_TIR57
11_Testing				
TEST_1	Penetration testing		Conduct regular penetration testing to identify and mitigate vulnerabilities by third parties and internally	BSI TR-03161-2 , AAMI_TIR57, IEC 81001-5-1
TEST_2	Security requirements testing		Internal tests whether security requirements are met	IEC 81001-5-1, AAMI_TIR57
TEST_3	Threat mitigation testing		Test the ability and effectiveness against threats identified in the threat modeling	IEC 81001-5-1, AAMI_TIR57
TEST_4	Vulnerability testing		The application should be regularly tested/assessed for vulnerabilities	IEC 81001-5-1
TEST_5	Static code analysis		Use of tools for static code analysis of the source code.	TR_03161, IEC 81001-5-1
12_Consent				
PURP_1	Defined purpose		The application/device should have a clear purpose	
PURP_2	User consent		Obtain a declaration of consent from the user, only consented data should be used.	TR_03161
PURP_3	Directory of consent		Maintain a directory of user consents.	TR_03161
PURP_4	Withdrawal of consent		Users should be able to withdraw their consent	TR_03161
13_Third Party Components				
THRD_1	Limitation of third-party components		Use only required third-party software and components	TR_03161
THRD_2	Up-to-date third-party components		Use of current version in third-party software or components	TR_03161
THRD_3	Maintenance of third-party components		The manufacturer should check the maintenance of third-party software/components used over the devices life cycle.	TR_03161
THRD_4	Trustworthiness of the source of third-party software		Third-party software and components should only be retrieved from trusted sources.	TR_03161
THRD_5	(S)BOM		The manufacturer should provide a centralized and complete list of dependencies from third party software.	TR_03161
THRD_6	Updates of third-party components		Security concept for installation of security updates for third-party software.	TR_03161
THRD_7	Sending data to third-party components/software		Sensitive data should not be sent to third-party software if not necessary.	TR_03161
THRD_8	Incoming data from third-party components/software		Validation of incoming data via third-party software.	TR_03161
THRD_9	Secure third-party components/software		Third-party suppliers should perform security life cycle activities	IEC 81001-5-1

THRD_10	Protection for external services	Protective functions at interfaces for external services	TR_03161
---------	----------------------------------	--	----------

Table S2. Mapping of FDA cybersecurity requirements for medical devices.

Code	Aspect	Description
General		
	Risk minimisation regarding known vulnerabilities	A device should be designed to eliminate or mitigate known vulnerabilities. Vulnerabilities identified in Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) Known Exploited Vulnerabilities Catalog should be designed out of the device
	Cybersecurity Design	FDA recommends that device manufacturers' design processes include design inputs for cybersecurity controls.
	Security in Context	Cybersecurity activities and device specifications should consider the intended use and the operating environment
	Deny by default	Design devices to "deny by default" (i.e., that which is not expressly permitted by a device is denied by default)
	Security by design/default	Design devices such that the potential impact of vulnerabilities is limited by specifying a secure configuration. Secure configurations may include endpoint protections, such as anti-malware, firewall/firewall rules, allow-listing, defining security event parameters, logging parameters, physical security detection, and/or HIDS/HIPS.
Auth		
	Use appropriate authentication	Use appropriate user authentication (e.g., multi-factor authentication to permit privileged device access to system administrators, service technicians, or maintenance personnel, among others, as needed)
	Authentication and authorisation for critical functionality	Require authentication, and authorization in certain instances, before permitting software or firmware updates, including those updates affecting the operating system, applications, and anti-malware functionality
	Authentication failures	Consider how the device and/or system should respond in event of authentication failure(s)
	Principle of Least Privileges	the principle of least privileges should be applied
	Access limitation	Limit authorized access to devices through the authentication of users
	Automatic time out	Use automatic timed methods to terminate sessions within the medical device system where appropriate for the use environment
Data		
	Data Accessibility	cybersecurity controls should not be intended to prohibit a user from accessing their device data.
	Anti replay measures/Data validity	Implement anti-replay measures in critical communications such as potentially harmful commands
	Verify Data Authenticity	Provide mechanisms for verifying the authenticity of information originating from the device, such as telemetry
	Data integrity	Verify the integrity of all incoming data, ensuring that it is not modified in transit or at rest
	Data validity	Validate that all data originating from external sources is well-formed and compliant with the expected protocol or specification. Additionally, as appropriate, validate data ranges to ensure they fall within safe limits

	Data integrity protection	Protect the integrity of data necessary to ensure the safety and effectiveness of the device, e.g., critical configuration settings such as energy output.
	Secure Sensitive Data at Rest	Sensitive Data at transit should be encrypted
	Secure Sensitive Data at Transit	Sensitive Data at rest should be encrypted
	Runtime code integrity verification	Use industry-accepted best practices to maintain and verify integrity of code while it is being executed on the device
	Recovery of device configuration	Design devices to provide methods for retention and recovery of trusted default device configuration by an authenticated, authorized user
Cryptography		
	Strong Cryptographic Algorithms	Select industry-standard cryptographic algorithms and protocols, and select appropriate key generation, distribution, management and protection, as well as robust nonce mechanisms.
	Strong Cryptographic Algorithms	Use current NIST recommended standards for cryptography or equivalent-strength cryptographic protection
	Strong Cryptographic Algorithms	Implement cryptographic protocols that permit negotiated parameters/versions such that the most recent, secure configurations are used, unless otherwise necessary.
	Strong Cryptographic Algorithms	Use cryptographically strong authentication schemes
	Hardware-based security	Hardware-based security solutions should be considered and employed when possible
	Avoid CRC	Do not rely on cyclic redundancy checks (CRCs) as security controls
Architecture		
	Security by design	Implementation of security controls should be applied across the system architecture
	Authentication of external connections	Authenticate external connections at a frequency commensurate with the associated risks
	Defense in depth	Design a system architecture and implement security controls to prevent a situation where the full compromise of any single device can result in the ability to reveal keys for other devices.
	Secure Update Mechanism	Digitally and physically Authenticate firmware, software, and devices
	Secure Update Mechanism	Allow installation of cryptographically authenticated firmware and software updates, and do not allow installation where such cryptographic authentication either is absent or fails
	Validate software prior execution	Ensure that the authenticity of software, firmware, and configuration are validated prior to execution
	Forensic evidence/Logging system	Ensure the design enables forensic evidence capture. The design should include mechanisms to securely create and store log files off the device to track security events.
	Updateability	Design devices to anticipate the need for software and firmware patches and updates to address future cybersecurity vulnerabilities
	Secure Update Mechanism	Consider update process reliability and how update process works in event of communication interruption or failure
	Security updates independent of cycle	Consider cybersecurity patches and updates that are independent of regular feature update cycles
	Ensure application of updates	Implement processes, technologies, security architectures, and exercises to facilitate the rapid verification, validation, and distribution of patches and updates.
	Trusted update channels	Implement a secure process and mechanism for providing validated software updates and patches for users.

	Cybersecurity interoperability	Cybersecurity controls should be used as a means to allow for the safe and effective exchange and use of information with other systems
	Endpoint security	Design devices such that they may integrate and/or leverage antivirus/anti-malware protection capabilities.
	Permit tracking and control of software changes	Design devices to enable software configuration management and permit tracking and control of software changes to be electronically obtainable (i.e., machine readable) by authorized users.
	Forbid downgrades	Do not allow downgrades, or version rollbacks, unless absolutely necessary for safety reasons, and log and document the event
Network		
Passwords		
	No hardcoded passwords	Do not use passwords that are hardcoded
	Strong password rules	Do not use passwords that are default, easily guessed, or easily compromised
Resilience		
	Disable debug ports	Disable or otherwise restrict unauthorized access to all test and debug ports prior to delivering products
	Physical security	Employ tamper evident seals on device enclosures and their sensitive communication ports to help verify physical integrity
	Resilience of sub systems and components	Design devices to specify the level of resilience, or independent ability to function, that any component of the medical device system possesses when its communication capabilities with the rest of the medical device system are disrupted, including disruption of significant duration
Source Code/Software Development		
	Coding best practices	manufacturers must implement a development processes that account for and address software risks throughout the design and development process as part of design controls
	Secure Product Development Framework	Develop and use a Secure Product Development Framework (SPDF)
	control of device source code	device manufacturers should establish and maintain custodial control of device source code
	Secure development environment	Preserve and maintain full build environments and virtual machines, regression test suites, engineering development kits, emulators, debuggers, and other related tools that were used to develop and test the original product to ensure updates and patches may be applied safely and in a timely manner
	Incident Detection/Security by design	Implement design features that allow for security compromises and suspected compromise attempts to be detected, recognized, logged, timed, and acted upon during normal use
	Vulnerability Detection/Security by design	Design devices to facilitate the performance of variant analyses such that the same vulnerabilities can be identified across device models and product lines.
	Segmentation of critical functions	Implement features that protect critical functionality and data, even when the device has been partially compromised
	Security by Design	Design devices to be resilient to possible cyber incident scenarios such as network outages, Denial of Service, excessive bandwidth usage by other products, disrupted quality of service (QoS), and/or excessive jitter
	Input Sanitation	Design devices to be resilient to possible noise items
Risk Management		

	Security Management	Risk	software device manufacturers may need to establish cybersecurity risk management and validation processes
	Security Management	Risk	Manufacturers should ensure they have appropriate resources to identify, assess, and mitigate cybersecurity vulnerabilities as they are identified throughout the supported device lifecycle
	Security Management	Risk	These processes should also ensure that risk control measures for one type of risk assessment do not inadvertently introduce new risks in the other.
	Life-Cycle Approach		Security risk management should be an integrated part of a manufacturer's entire quality system, addressed throughout the TPLC.
	Security Management Plan	Risk	Generate a security risk management plan, e.g. in accordance with AAMI TIR 57
	Risk assessment		FDA recommends that device manufacturers conduct both a safety risk assessment and a separate, accompanying security risk assessment to ensure a more comprehensive identification and management of patient safety risks.
	Risk assessment		when any known vulnerabilities are only partially mitigated or unmitigated by the device design, they should be assessed as reasonably foreseeable risks in the risk assessment and be assessed for additional control measures or risk transfer ³⁵ to the user/operator, or, if necessary, the patient.
	Risk assessment		A cybersecurity risk assessment should be conducted which focusses on exploitabilities
	Risk assessment		The cybersecurity risk assessment is non-probabilistic
	Risk assessment		security risk assessment processes focus on exploitability, or the ability to exploit vulnerabilities present within a device and/or system.
	Risk assessment		manufacturers should assess identified risks according to the level of risk posed from the device and the system in which it operates.
	Risk assessment		If post market exploits are not applicable to unreleased software, a premarket exploitability assessment could either assume a worstcase assessment and implement appropriate controls, or provide a justification for a reasonable exploitability assessment of the risk throughout the TPLC and how the risk is controlled.
	Risk assessment		Acceptance criteria for cybersecurity risks should carefully consider the TPLC of the medical device system
	Risk assessment		known vulnerabilities should be assessed as reasonably foreseeable risks
	Risk assessment TPLC		The cybersecurity risk assessment should consider the TPLC
	Risk assessment		Security risk assessments that include analyses and considerations of cybersecurity risks that may exist in or be introduced by third-party software and the software supply chain could be conducted
	Risk assessment		For components with known vulnerabilities, device manufacturers should provide Details of applicable safety and security risk controls to address the vulnerability.
	Risk assessment		the assessment for impacts to safety and effectiveness may include an assessment for the potential security impacts of anomalies including consideration of any present Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) categories
	Risk Transfer		Any risks transferred to the user should be detailed and considered for inclusion as tasks during usability testing
	Risk Transfer		Risk transfer, if appropriate, should only occur when all relevant risk information is known, assessed, and appropriately communicated to users
	Threat Modeling		Conduct Threat Modeling
	Threat Modeling		The threat model should identify medical device system risks and mitigations as well as inform the pre- and post-mitigation risks considered as part of the cybersecurity risk assessment;

	Threat Modeling	The threat model should State any assumptions about the medical device system or environment of use
	Threat Modeling	The threat model should Capture cybersecurity risks introduced through the supply chain, manufacturing, deployment, interoperation with other devices, maintenance/update activities, and decommission activities
	Risk Measures and Metrics	measures and metrics for the assessment over the TPLC should be defined and measured
	Risk Measures and Metrics	Risk measures and metrics could include Percentage of identified vulnerabilities that are updated or patched (defect density);
	Risk Measures and Metrics	Risk measures and metrics could include Duration from vulnerability identification to when it is updated or patched
	Risk Measures and Metrics	Risk measures and metrics could include Duration from when an update or patch is available to complete implementation in devices deployed in the field, to the extent known.
	Check vulnerability databases	Cybersecurity management plans should include Identify and address vulnerabilities identified in CISA Known Exploited Vulnerabilities Catalog
	Known Vulnerabilites	For each known vulnerability, manufacturers should describe how the vulnerabilities were discovered to demonstrate whether the assessment methods were sufficiently robust.
	Known Vulnerabilites	For components with known vulnerabilities, device manufacturers should provide A safety and security risk assessment of each known vulnerability
	Reporting of security-related issues	Cybersecurity management plans should include Description of their coordinated vulnerability disclosure process
	User notification in case of incidents	Design devices to notify users when malfunctions or anomalous device behavior, including those potentially related to a cybersecurity breach, are detected.
Testing		
	Testing	FDA recommends verification and validation include sufficient testing performed by the manufacturer on the cybersecurity of the medical device system through which the manufacturer verifies and validates their inputs and outputs
	Security requirements testing	Security requirements testing
	Threat mitigation testing	Threat Mitigation testing
	Vulnerability testing	Vulnerability testing (e.g., Fuzz Testing, Static and dynamic code analysis, attack surface analysis)
	Penetration testing	Penetration testing
	Static code analysis/Code Review	Carefully design and review all code that handles the parsing of external data using automated (e.g., static and dynamic analyses) and manual (i.e., code review) methods
	Life Cycle Approach	FDA recommends that cybersecurity testing should occur throughout the TPLC
Consent/GDPR		
Third Party Components		
	Risk management	Third party software components should be assessed for cybersecurity risks
	Risk management	Third party software components risks should be addressed or mitigated
	Risk management	security risks of the third party software components should become factors of the overall medical device system risk management processes and documentation
	Third-party update	manufacturers should include plans for how third-party software components could be updated or replaced if support ends or other software issues arise

	SBOM	An SBOM should be provided and maintained that includes the device manufacturer-developed components and thirdparty components
	SBOM	The SBOM should be machine readable, and contain the minimum requirements of the National Telecommunications and Information Administration (NTIA) Multistakeholder Process, the the level of support, and the end of support date
	Third-party licencies	Maintain necessary third-party licenses throughout the supported lifespan of the device.
	Third-party EoS	Develop contingency plans for the possibility that a third-party company goes out of business or stops supporting a licensed product.
User instructions/Communication		
	User Cybersecurity Information	Manufacturers should inform users of relevant security information
	Transparency of network ports	Provision of a list of network ports and other interfaces that are expected to receive and/or send data to users.
	User instruction	User should be provided with instructions that allow them to manage risks associated with the software components, including known vulnerabilities, configuration specifications, and other relevant security and risk management considerations
	User instruction	Sufficiently detailed diagrams for users that allow recommended cybersecurity controls to be implemented
	User instruction	Specific guidance to users regarding supporting infrastructure requirements so that the device can operate as intended
	Update instructions	A description of systematic procedures for users to download version-identifiable manufacturer-authorized software and firmware, including a description of how users will know when software is available.
	User information	FDA recommends that manufacturers establish a plan for how they will identify and communicate to users vulnerabilities that are identified after releasing the device
Documentation		
	Documentation	Manufacturers should submit documentation in their premarket submissions demonstrating that the security controls for the categories above, and further detailed in the recommendations in Appendix 1, have (1) been implemented, and (2) been tested in order to validate that they were effectively implemented
	Security in context	Device instructions and product specifications related to recommended cybersecurity controls appropriate for the intended use environment
	Labeling Recommendation	A description of how the design enables the device to respond when anomalous conditions are detected
	Labeling Recommendation	A high-level description of the device features that protect critical functionality
	Labeling Recommendation	A description of backup and restore features and procedures to restore authenticated configurations.
	Labeling Recommendation	A description of methods for retention and recovery of device configuration by an authenticated authorized user.
	Labeling Recommendation	A description of the secure configuration of shipped devices, instructions for userconfigurable changes, and identification of user-configurable changes that could increase security risk for the medical device system
	Labeling Recommendation	Where appropriate for the intended use environment, a description of how forensic evidence is captured, including but not limited to any log files kept for a security event.
	Labeling Recommendation	Information, if known or anticipated, concerning device cybersecurity (including components) end of support and end of life.
	Labeling Recommendation	Information on securely decommissioning devices by sanitizing the product of sensitive, confidential, and proprietary data and software.

	security risk management reports	include security risk management reports in submission
	security risk management reports	The security risk management report should include the documentation elements for the system threat modeling, cybersecurity risk assessment, Software Bill of Materials (SBOM), component support information, vulnerability assessments, and unresolved anomaly assessment(s)
	security risk management reports	the security risk management report should Summarize the risk evaluation methods and processes
	security risk management reports	the security risk management report should Detail the residual risk conclusion from the security risk assessment,
	security risk management reports	the security risk management report should Detail the risk mitigation activities undertaken
	security risk management reports	the security risk management report should Provide traceability between the threat model, cybersecurity risk assessment, SBOM, and testing documentation
	Threat model documentation	Provide Threat modeling documentation
	Update of documentation	manufacturers should update their security risk management documentation as new information becomes available
	Update of documentation	The risk management documentation should account for all versions of the device
	Security architecture views	Different security architecture views should be provided, at a minimum Global System View; • Multi-Patient Harm View; • Updateability/Patchability View; and • Security Use Case View(s)
	Security architecture views	The security architecture views should Identify security-relevant medical device system elements and their interfaces
	Security architecture views	The security architecture views should Establish traceability of architecture elements to user and medical device system security requirements.
	Security architecture views	FDA recommends that manufacturers develop and maintain security architecture view documentation as a part of the process for the design, development, and maintenance of the medical device system
	Cybersecurity Management Plan	Cybersecurity management plans should include Personnel responsible
	Cybersecurity Management Plan	Cybersecurity management plans should include Sources, methods, and frequency for monitoring and identifying vulnerabilities
	Cybersecurity management plan	Cybersecurity management plans should include Timeline to develop and release patches
	Cybersecurity management plan	Cybersecurity management plans should include Update processes
	Cybersecurity management plan	Cybersecurity management plans should include Patching capability
	Cybersecurity management plan	Cybersecurity management plans should include Description of how the manufacturer intends to communicate forthcoming remediations, patches, and updates to customers

Table S3. Mapping of MDCG 2019-16 cybersecurity requirements for medical devices.

Code	Aspect	Description
General		
	Third Party Auditing	Auditability that supports non-repudiation

	Security in Context	Assess reasonable level of security for the operating environment
	Security by Design (SbD)	the product should be Secure by design
	Life-Cycle Approach	The PMS system should update the design and manufacturing information, the instructions for use and the labelling;
	Security in Context	Establish appropriate security measures for the use of mobile devices and teleworking.
	Life-Cycle Approach	Security, safety and effectiveness should be considered over the devices life cycle
	Security Capabilities for MD	Audit Controls
	Security Capabilities for MD	Configuration of Security Features
	Security Capabilities for MD	Security and Privacy Guides
	Security in Context	operating environment must provide physical security, e.g., through authenticated physical access, segregation, access policy
	Life-Cycle Approach	The post-market cybersecurity surveillance program should include sharing and dissemination of cybersecurity information and knowledge of cybersecurity vulnerabilities and threats across multiple sectors
	Security in Context	Consider Intended use
	Security in Context	Consider operational environment
	Security in Context	Good physical security
	Security by default	Secure configuration of the system at integration
	Security in Context	The operator is responsible for a secure operational environment
	Security in context	Interaction between software and the IT environment
	Regulatory Landscape	The operator must be in line with national and EU regulations
	Security Capabilities for MD	Personal Data Integrity and Authenticity
	Security in context	Physical Locks
	Security in context	Manufacturer should determine the minimum requirements for their devices operating environment
	Security Capabilities for MD	Appropriate security controls
	Security in context	measures should be implemented at the operator site in a time appropriate to the security and safety risk
Auth		
	Access Management	Methods for authentication and authorisation should be appropriate to the device
	Session Management	Automatic Logoff
	Access Management	Emergency Access
	Access Management	Person Authentication
	Session Management	Session management measures
	Principle of Least Privileges	Apply the principle of least privilege to user workstations and connected devices. o Least privileges must also take into account data minimisation per role.
	Role Based Access Control	Access control measures (e.g. role based)

	Network Access control	Network access controls, such as segmentation
	Access Management	User access management
	Unauthorised access	Protection against Unauthorised access
Data		Data
	Personal Data	Personal Data De-Identification
	Backup/Recovery	Data Backup and Disaster Recovery
	Personal Data	Personal Data Storage Confidentiality
	Secure Data at Transit	Transmission Confidentiality
	Secure Data at Transit	Transmission Integrity
	Secure Data at Transit	Data encryption
	Data integrity	Data integrity should be ensured e.g. through hashing, integrity checks.
	Backup/Recovery	Implement data recovery mechanisms to restore data from critical systems
Cryptography		
Architecture		
	Updatability	General patch management practices that ensure timely security patch updates
	Defense in Depth	Apply Defense in depth
	Updatability	Cybersecurity Product Upgrades
	Security interoperability	Interoperability and compatibility with other devices or products
	Security of devices	medical device should be as autonomous as possible in terms of IT security and sole reliance on the existence of any IT security requirements on the operating environment should be kept to a minimum
	Protection against arbitrary code execution	Memory protection measures to block arbitrary code execution
	Security in Context/Security Interoperability	Elements of the operating environment interacting with (e.g. other devices) or required for the operation of medical devices (e.g. OS) should ensure interoperability and shall not impair the specified performance of the medical device
	Security by Design	Operating system hardening and application whitelisting
	Security Interoperability	Compatibility of medical device management software with security solutions that counter malicious code
	Secure Update Mechanism	Provisions to ensure integrity/validation of software updates and security patches
	Endpoint Security	Antivirus / anti-malware software
	Security requirements	Conduct a Specification of security requirements to identify required security capabilities for the device
Network		
	Firewalls	Protection of devices with firewalls
	Control and security of network traffic	operating environment must provide control and security of network traffic
	Control and security of network traffic	Network segmentation
	Control and security of network traffic	Traffic filtering

	Segmentation	Partitioning mechanisms and network / traffic segmentation
	Workstation Security	Application whitelisting / system hardening
	Secure network environment	Node Authentication
Passwords		
	Strong Password Rules	Use sufficiently complex passwords
Resilience		
	Integrity check of end device	Software integrity checks and device authentication mechanisms
Source Code/Software Development		
Risk Management		
	Risk acceptance	security risk has to be reduced to an acceptable level
	Security risk management	Risk management should consider reasonably foreseeable misuse
	Notifications	Notification of the manufacturer in case of events
	Security risk management	Management of security-related issues
	Security risk management	Security risk management is part of the process of the general risk management process
	Safety risk management	Security risks or controls with safety impact should be included in the safety risk assessment
	Security risk management	Safety risks or controls that have a security impact should be included in the security risk assessment
	Safety risk management	The safety risk assessment should list generic security related hazards (e.g., denial of service) without detailing every possible security attack vector
	Threat Modeling	Conduct Threat modelling to identify device vulnerabilities
	Vulnerability identification	Assess the relevance vulnerabilities, e.g., their risk, how they affect safety, etc.
	Benefit-Risk Analysis	For security risks, an overall Benefit Risk Analysis is to be executed based on the intended use and possible safety and performance impact
	PMS	Post-market surveillance should include Security incidents directly related to medical device software
	PMS	Post-market surveillance should include Security Vulnerabilities that are related to the medical device hardware/software and the 3rd party hardware/software used with the medical device.
	PMS	Post-market surveillance should include Changes in the threat landscape, including interoperability aspects
	Life-cycle approach	The manufacturer should evaluate the information thus gathered, evaluate the associated security and safety risk and take appropriate measures that control the risk associated with such security incidents or vulnerabilities
	Response Plan	Documented action plan for the user to follow in case of an alert message
	PMS	The post-market cybersecurity surveillance program should include vulnerability remediation
	PMS	The post-market cybersecurity surveillance program should include incident response
	PMS	The PMS system should update the benefit-risk determination and to improve the risk management;

	Notify Authorities	Serious incidents and field safety corrective actions must be reported to the competent authority
	Notify Authorities	Incidents that have cybersecurity related incident root causes are subject to Trend Reporting
	Risk Assessment	Conduct a risk assessment and impact assessment. Introduction of medical devices in the environment should be subject to such a risk assessment.
	Security in context	The Health Information System (HIS) must be able to monitor the correct operation of the equipment. o Monitor device behaviour in the context of medical workflows.
	Response Plan/Life-cycle approach	Investigate major incidents and review actions taken to mitigate and reduce time to react to future occurrences.
	Response Plan	Develop a disaster recovery plan, taking into account the minimum recovery requirements.
	Risk Assessment	IT security requirement for the operating environment should be based on the risk assessment
	Life Cycle Approach	The post-market cybersecurity surveillance program should include operation of the device in the intended environment
	cyber smart behavior	Users are encouraged to employ cyber smart behavior
	Benefit-Risk Analysis	Risks of to weak and to restrictive security
	Training	Security awareness training
	Risk Assessment	The exploitation of unknown vulnerabilities should be considered as reasonably foreseeable misuse
	Training	Provide required documentation and training
	Patchability	Provide support for patching and security incident handling
	Risk Assessment	include security issues in the risk assessment
	Security risk management	Implement Security management
	Security requirements	When determining security capabilities, the manufacturer should demonstrate for each security measure that not only the goals of safety and effectiveness are maintained with the implementation of a specific capability, but also performance requirements and the existing risk control measures remain effective as specified
	Device catalogue	Catalogue assets in an inventory of all medical devices, servers and workstations.
	Risk Control Measure	Quick fixes, e.g. network configuration changes
	PMS	A Post-market surveillance system should be put in place
	PMS	The PMS system should update the clinical evaluation
	Security Policies	A set of baseline IT security policies should be defined, approved by management and communicated to employees and relevant external parties, including roles, password policy, etc.
Testing		
	Testing	Security verification and validation testing should be used to ensure that security requirements are met
	Testing	To allow security verification and validation, testing should be conducted
	Security requirements testing	To allow security verification and validation, testing should be conducted
	Vulnerability testing	fuzz testing
	Vulnerability testing	vulnerability scanning
	Penetration testing	penetration testing
	Static code analysis	Use tools for secure code analysis

	Testing of updates	security updates and security patches should be tested for regressions and made available to product users in a timely manner
	Static code analysis	Use tools that scan for open source code and libraries used in the product, to identify components with known issues
Consent/GDPR		
Third Party Components		
	Limitation of third-party components	Install only software programmes necessary for the intended use of the operating environment.
	Supervision of third-party components	Modification of a medical device, e.g. the installation or enabling of third-party software including software patching, should always be under explicit published guidance of the manufacturer.
	Trustworthy third-party-components	Exclusive use of genuine software and ban of all illegitimate software and applications
	EoL of Third Party components	Avoid the use of End of life third-party components and devices on the operating environment, where possible take additional measures such as network isolation.
	Changes of Third Party Components	Monitor and keep track of changes in ecosystem parties, so that business processes are not interrupted or hide risks.
User instructions/Communication		
	User instructions	The instruction for use should provide information on the risk assessment for the device as regards to IT security risks
	User instructions	The instruction could include high level summary of risk profile of the medical device and the corresponding IT security objectives
	User instructions	The instruction could include Specifications of the operating system
	User instructions	The instruction should include information about the installation, configuration and operation of the medical device
	Security by default	Security configuration options; in accordance with the security-by-default principle, the medical device should have the highest possible security settings selected by default.
	User instructions	The instruction could include Product installation
	User instructions	The instruction could include Initial configuration guidelines, e.g. change of default passwords during first login.
	User instructions	The instruction could include Step-by-step instructions for deploying security updates
	User instructions	The instruction could include Procedures for using the medical device in failsafe mode (e.g. enter/exit failsafe mode, performance restrictions in failsafe mode, data recovery function when resuming normal operation etc.)
	User instructions	The user instruction should include information about the secure configuration and application of security updates for the medical device
	User instructions	The user instruction should outline compatibility issues as regards to the operating environment (software, hardware etc.) and any compatibility restrictions
	User instructions	The user instruction should adequately describe the requirements regarding the operating environment (hardware, network characteristics, security controls etc.)
	User instructions	The instruction could include Assumptions on the environment of use (e.g. home environment, healthcare facility etc.)
	User instructions	A description of backup and restore features for both data and configuration settings
	User instructions	Device instructions for use and product specifications related to recommended cybersecurity controls appropriate for the intended use environment (e.g., anti-virus software, use of a firewall, etc.).

	User instructions	Description of device features that protect critical functionality, even when the device's cybersecurity has been compromised (e.g. Operating System hardening).
	User instructions	Description of backup and restore features and procedures to regain configurations.
	User instructions	Specific guidance to users regarding supporting infrastructure requirements so that the device can operate as intended.
	Information for providers	Description of how the device is or can be hardened using secure configuration. Secure configurations may include end point protections such as anti-malware, firewall/firewall rules, whitelisting, security event parameters, logging parameters, physical security detection, etc.
	Information for providers	List of network ports and other interfaces that are expected to receive/send data, and a description of port functionality and whether the ports are incoming or outgoing (Unused ports should be disabled).
	Information for providers	Sufficiently detailed network diagrams for end-users.
	Information for providers	Where appropriate, technical instructions to permit secure network (connected) deployment and servicing, and instructions for users on how to respond upon detection of a cybersecurity vulnerability or incident.
	Information for providers	Where appropriate, risks of using the medical device outside of the intended use environment.
	User instructions	Recommended IT security controls for operating environment (e.g. anti-virus, firewall)
	Up-to-date User instructions	The Manufacturer should update the instructions if needed
	Information for providers	The MDS2 is an industry-wide and globally accepted form, which can be used to provide the abovementioned security information.
	Tailored user instructions	Provision of information for Medical Device Software (MDSW) users should be tailored to where the device is used
	Turn off features	User information should inform users to be able to Turn of features that are not used
	Minimum requirements	Instruction should contain Minimum requirements for the workstations intended for user operations: hardware features, operating system versions, peripheral devices, etc.
	Minimum requirements	Instruction should contain Minimum platform requirements for the connected medical device: hardware properties, operating system versions, middleware and drivers, peripheral devices, etc
	Information for operators	Information to operators of medical devices on the identified risk and possible mitigations in the operating environment
	User instructions	Instructions should contain Risks for device operation outside the intended operating environment
	User instructions	Clinicians/physicians should be provided with the information they need to have meaningful discussion with their patients about the risks and benefits of the device they use, including cybersecurity risks.
Documentation		
	Up-to-date Security informations	Security information should be kept up-to-date
	Documentation	technical documentation should include security requirements to ensure safety and effectiveness of products against security risks and threats, and a justification, validation and verification of the solutions adopted to meet those requirements
	Up-to-date documentation	technical documentation needs to be updated with information raised through the manufacturers post market surveillance system related to handling and remediation of cybersecurity incidents and vulnerabilities

	User instructions	The manufacturer shall provide clear documentation of the device's instructions for use, including IT security features/configurations
	Security Guidelines	The manufacturer should create and maintain security guidelines
	SBOM	Software Bill of Materials for security information sharing

Table S4. Comparison of the created cybersecurity requirements list with FDA_Cyber and MDCG 2019-16

Code	Aspect	FDA_Cyber	MDCG 2019-16
01_General Principles		6/9	6,5/10
GNRL_1	Life-Cycle Approach	1	1
GNRL_2	Security by Design (SbD)	1	1
GNRL_3	Security by Default	1	1
GNRL_4	Usable Security	0	0,5
GNRL_5	No Security through Obscurity	1	0
GNRL_6	Security in Context	1	1
GNRL_7	Third Party Auditing	0	1
GNRL_8	End-Of-Life	0	0
GNRL_9	Documentation	1	1
02_Auth & Access Control		5,5/16	4,5/16
AUTH_1	Principle of Least Privileges	1	1
AUTH_2	Role Based Access Control	0,5	1
AUTH_3	Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA)	1	0
AUTH_4	Separation of authentication and authorization	0	0
AUTH_5	Session Management	1	1
AUTH_6	Re-authentication in active use	0	0
AUTH_7	Re-authentication after interruption	0	0
AUTH_8	Re-authentication after inactivity	1	1
AUTH_9	Invalidation of identification tokens	0	0
AUTH_10	Change of authentication data	0	0
AUTH_11	Change of access parameters	0	0
AUTH_12	Deletion of identification tokens	0	0
AUTH_13	Access Logging	1	0
AUTH_14	Unusual login attempts	0	0,5
AUTH_15	Brute Force Login attempts	0	0
AUTH_16	Root of trust	0	0
03_Data Protection & Privacy		3/13	3/10
DATA_1	Privacy-preserving design	0	0
DATA_2	Minimal access to sensitive data	0	0

DATA_3	Secure Data at Rest	1	1
DATA_4	Secure Data at Transit	1	1
DATA_5	Secure Data at Use	0	0
DATA_6	Encrypted Backups	0	0
DATA_7	No Key-logging	0	0
DATA_8	No clipboard exports	0	0
DATA_9	No export of biometric data or keys	0	0
DATA_10	Blocking of screen access	0	0
DATA_11	Third-party data access	0	0
DATA_12	Data Minimisation	0	0
DATA_13	Verifying data validity	1	1
04_Cryptography		4,5/8	0,5/8
CRYP_1	Strong Cryptographic Algorithms	1	0,5
CRYP_2	Key Management	0,5	0
CRYP_3	Strong Cryptographic Keys	1	0
CRYP_4	Protection of cryptographic keys	0	0
CRYP_5	No hard-coded keys or other secrets	1	0
CRYP_6	Purpose limitation of cryptographic keys	0	0
CRYP_7	Proven Implementations	1	0
CRYP_8	Strong, secure random number generation	0	0
05_Architecture		7/10	4/10
ARCH_1	Secure Update Mechanism	1	1
ARCH_2	Trusted update channels	1	0
ARCH_3	Ensure application of updates	1	1
ARCH_4	Central logging system	1	0
ARCH_5	Endpoint security	1	1
ARCH_6	Localised processing logic	0	0
ARCH_7	Management interfaces	0	0
ARCH_8	Defense in Depth	1	1
ARCH_9	Attack Surface reduction	0	0
ARCH_10	Design/Architecture reviews	1	0
06_Network		1,5/8	4/8
NETW_1	Network Security	0	1
NETW_2	Encryption of Network Communication	1	1
NETW_3	Certificate Chain	0	0
NETW_4	Support for certificate-pinning	0	0
NETW_5	Validation of Backend Systems	0	0
NETW_6	Log Files	0	0
NETW_7	Firewalls	0,5	1

NETW_8	Separation of communication channels	0	1
07_Passwords		3/6	3/6
PWRD_1	Strong Password Rules	1	1
PWRD_2	Display password strength when creating it	0	0
PWRD_3	Option for password changes	1	1
PWRD_4	Logging of password changes	0	0
PWRD_5	Storage of passwords	0	0
PWRD_6	No hardcoded passwords	1	1
08_Resilience		1/5	1/5
RESI_1	Detection of debug environment	0	0
RESI_2	Unusual user rights detection	0	0
RESI_3	Integrity check of end device	1	1
RESI_4	Integrity check of backend system	0	0
RESI_5	Reverse engineering	0	0
09_Source Code/Software Development		3/7	0/7
SOUR_1	Coding Best Practises	1	0
SOUR_2	Input sanitation	1	0
SOUR_3	Prevention against injection of functionalities	0	0
SOUR_4	No sensitive data in messages.	0	0
SOUR_5	Secure productive version	0	0
SOUR_6	Secure development environment	1	0
SOUR_7	Automation Tools	0	0
10_Risk Management		10/11	10/11
RISK_1	Continuous Monitoring	1	1
RISK_2	Incident Response Plan	1	1
RISK_3	Threat Modeling	1	1
RISK_4	Check vulnerability databases	1	1
RISK_5	User instructions	1	1
RISK_6	Quality Management System	0	0
RISK_7	Security Training	1	1
RISK_8	Security Risk Management	1	1
RISK_9	User reporting	1	1
RISK_10	Reporting of security-related issues	1	1
RISK_11	Benefit Risk analysis	1	1
11_Testing		5/5	5/5
TEST_1	Penetration testing	1	1
TEST_2	Security requirements testing	1	1
TEST_3	Threat mitigation testing	1	1
TEST_4	Vulnerability testing	1	1

TEST_5	Static code analysis	1	1
12_ Consent		0/4	0/4
PURP_1	Defined purpose	0	0
PURP_2	User consent	0	0
PURP_3	Directory of consent	0	0
PURP_4	Withdrawal of consent	0	0
13_ Third Party Components		4/10	4,5/10
THRD_1	Limitation of third-party componenets	0	1
THRD_2	Up-to-date third-party componenets	1	0
THRD_3	Maintenance of third-party components	1	0,5
THRD_4	Trustworthiness of the source of third-party software	0	1
THRD_5	(S)BOM	1	1
THRD_6	Updates of third-party components	1	0
THRD_7	Sending data to third-party components/software	0	0
THRD_8	Incoming data from third-party components/software	0	0
THRD_9	Secure third-party components/software	0	1
THRD_10	Protection for external sevicees	0	0